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TrialsNet: TRials supported by Smart Networks beyond 5G

Deliverable D7.3

**Open Call report on achieved results and
allocation of Grants**

Project Details

Call	HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022
Type of Action	HORIZON-JU-IA HORIZON JU Innovation Actions
Project start date	01/01/2023
Duration	36 months
Grant Agreement No.	101095871

Deliverable Details

Deliverable WP:	WP7
Deliverable Task:	T7.3
Deliverable Identifier:	TrialsNet D7.3
Deliverable Title:	Open Call report on achieved results and allocation of Grants
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Contractual Date of Delivery:	31/12/2025
Submission Date:	23/12/2025
Dissemination Level:	PU
Status:	Final
Version:	1.0
File Name:	2025-12-23_TrialsNet_D7.3_Open Call report on achieved results and allocation of Grants.docx

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Deliverable History

Version	Date	Modification
<i>V1.0</i>	<i>23/12/2025</i>	<i>Final version, submitted to EC through SyGMa</i>

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym	Description		
<i>3GPP</i>	3rd Generation Partnership Project	<i>KPI</i>	Key Performance Indicator
<i>5G</i>	5th Generation mobile Wireless Communication System	<i>KVI</i>	Key Value Indicator
<i>6G</i>	6th Generation mobile Wireless Communication System	<i>MR</i>	Monthly Report
<i>AIA</i>	Athens International Airport S.A.	<i>NXW</i>	Nextworks
<i>B5G</i>	Beyond 5th Generation mobile Wireless Communication System	<i>OC</i>	Open Call
<i>CERTH</i>	Center for Research and Technology Hellas	<i>OP</i>	Operational Plan
<i>CNIT</i>	Consorzio Nazionale Interuniversitario per le Telecomunicazioni	<i>ORO</i>	Orange
<i>CTE</i>	Culture, Tourism and Entertainment	<i>PIIU</i>	Promozione per l'Innovazione fra Industria e Università Associazione
<i>DAEM</i>	Dimos Athinaion Epicheirisi Michanografisis	<i>Q&A</i>	Questions and Answers
<i>EC</i>	European Commission	<i>R&I</i>	Research and Innovation
<i>EU</i>	European Union	<i>RW</i>	Real Wireless
<i>FMEA</i>	Failure Mode and Effects Analysis	<i>SNS JU</i>	Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
<i>GA</i>	Grant Agreement	<i>TEI</i>	Ericsson Telecomunicazioni S.p.A.
<i>GUI</i>	Graphical User Interface	<i>TID</i>	Telefonica Investigacion Y Desarrollo SA
<i>IEEE</i>	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers	<i>TIM</i>	Telecom Italia S.p.A. Telefonica Investigacion Y Desarrollo SA
<i>IMEC</i>	Interuniversitair Micro-Electronica Centrum	<i>TRL</i>	Technology Readiness Level
<i>IoT</i>	Internet of Things	<i>UC</i>	Use Case
<i>IPR</i>	Intellectual Property Rights	<i>UC3M</i>	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
<i>ITTS</i>	Infrastructure, Transport, Security & Safety	<i>VR</i>	Virtual Reality
		<i>WINGS</i>	WINGS ICT Solutions
		<i>WP</i>	Work Package
		<i>XR</i>	Work Package
			Extended Reality

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Executive Summary

This document builds upon and completes the Open Call (OC) activities implemented within Work Package 7 (WP7), following the preparatory and execution phases documented in Deliverables D7.1 [1] and D7.2 [2]. The first deliverable of Task 7, D7.1 describes the established foundational framework of the TrialsNet OC by defining its scope, objectives, eligibility conditions, legal and administrative procedures, evaluation criteria and supporting technical material, thereby enabling third parties to prepare and submit high-quality proposals in alignment with the project's goals. Subsequently, D7.2 documented the operational execution of the OC, including its official launch, extensive promotion and communication activities, applicant support mechanisms (such as webinars, helpdesk services and feasibility checks), the structured proposal evaluation process and the final selection and contracting of the funded sub-projects.

In continuity with the activities reported above, D7.3 is focusing on the systematic monitoring, evaluation and assessment of the funded sub-projects throughout their full implementation lifecycle. A key element underpinning the success of the TrialsNet OC was the supportive and collaborative approach adopted by the consortium towards the sub-projects. Beyond its formal monitoring and evaluation role, WP7 implemented a continuous assistance model aimed at maximising the technical quality, alignment and impact of third-party activities. This included structured feasibility checks, regular technical interactions, monthly reports, review meetings, timely feedback on deliverables and ongoing helpdesk support, allowing early identification of risks and deviations and enabling corrective actions to be taken proactively. Rather than acting solely as a control mechanism, the evaluation framework functioned as an enabling process, fostering integration of sub-projects within the TrialsNet ecosystem and ensuring consistency with project objectives. This experience directly impacted the consortium's decisions on how to design, manage and refine OC procedures, demonstrating that a support-oriented governance model is essential for achieving high-quality outcomes and for establishing a robust, fair and replicable methodology for future Open Calls. In parallel with the internal OC activities, the TrialsNet consortium actively participated in the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) OC Task Force, contributing to cross-project coordination, exchange of best practices and alignment with the broader SNS JU framework. This participation enabled TrialsNet to benchmark its OC design, evaluation procedures and support mechanisms against other SNS JU initiatives, ensuring consistency with emerging programme-level recommendations. The insights gained through the Task Force informed several operational and governance decisions, particularly regarding applicant support, evaluation transparency and monitoring practices, reinforcing the robustness, fairness and replicability of the TrialsNet OC methodology. This engagement further strengthened the strategic positioning of the TrialsNet OC within the SNS JU ecosystem and enhanced its contribution to a harmonised European approach to third-party funding schemes.

In particular, this deliverable presents the complete monitoring, evaluation and grant-allocation framework applied during the implementation of the TrialsNet OC, documenting the activities undertaken by the consortium to ensure transparent, consistent, and high-quality execution of the 24 funded sub-projects. The OC sub-projects were implemented over a 12-month period (M1–M12), starting in May 2024, corresponding to Month 17 (M17) of the TrialsNet project and concluded in April 2025, corresponding to Month 28 (M28). The document outlines this operational timeline, the mechanisms adopted for continuous technical and administrative oversight and the multi-layered evaluation methodology used to assess progress, validate Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVI) and identify risks throughout the Open Call sub-projects' lifecycle.

The TrialsNet OC was designed and implemented as a mechanism to extend the project's technical activities, increase geographical coverage and enable large-scale validation of 5G/B5G-oriented technologies and use cases. Following the successful supportive approach of the feasibility checks, the consortium experts took actions to secure the full integration of the sub-projects within TrialsNet project through an extensive evaluation phase. The consortium developed a complete operational and evaluation framework, including templates, guidelines, KPIs and KVI report templates with reference to the relevant TrialsNet documents, monitoring tools, submission support services and transparent assessment procedures. To ensure transparent implementation and alignment with the TrialsNet objectives, WP7 applied a structured multi-stage evaluation and monitoring approach, combining formal review steps (Operational Plan, Mid-Term and Final reports), monthly technical monitoring and review meetings along with support activities. This evaluation framework was supported by a multi-layered expert team and a well-defined risk-based multi-criteria scoring methodology inspired by established

principles including Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) allowing for a graded risk classification and impact-oriented ranking and early identification of deviations and targeted mitigation actions.

As an outcome of WP7 activities, all 24 awarded sub-projects successfully completed their activities and demonstrated strong performance, validated through the final evaluation procedure. A dedicated internal assessment conducted among all participants further confirmed the clarity, transparency and effectiveness of the OC framework and the overall support structure provided by the consortium. Overall, the TrialsNet OC demonstrated the effectiveness of the adopted methodology not only in onboarding new stakeholders, but also in generating technically mature and measurable results that were systematically integrated into the project's core work packages. The platforms, network extensions and trial outcomes produced by the OC sub-projects were consolidated and incorporated into WP2, strengthening the final integration, deployment and validation of the TrialsNet infrastructure and platform solutions, as documented in Deliverable D2.3 [3] and D2.4 [4]. In parallel, the OC results directly reinforced the implementation and large-scale validation of use cases across the three vertical domains, with sub-project trials, datasets and technical enhancements contributing to the final outcomes reported in WP3 Infrastructure, Transport, Security and Safety (ITSS), WP4 eHealth and WP5 Culture, Tourism and Entertainment (CTE), as detailed in Deliverables D3.3 [5], D4.3 [6] and D5.3 [7] respectively. Furthermore, quantitative and qualitative data derived from the OC trials, including network-level KPIs, application-level performance indicators and socio-technical KVI were harmonised and integrated into the project-wide validation, impact assessment and dissemination framework of WP6. This integration strengthened the final KPI/KVI assessment and enabled comparative analysis between core project and OC trials, as comprehensively results reported in Deliverable D6.3 [8]. Through this structured integration of third-party results into both the technical and evaluation work streams, the TrialsNet substantially reinforced the project's scientific, operational and impact outcomes, while establishing a robust and replicable model.

In addition to the technical integration of Open Call results, the TrialsNet project significantly strengthened its overall impact through coordinated dissemination and standardisation activities. The outcomes of the OC trials were actively disseminated along with those of TrialsNet project through scientific publications, industrial events, cluster workshops and cross-project collaborations, ensuring broad visibility and uptake of the validated solutions. Moreover, technical insights, KPI/KVI evidence and lessons learned from large-scale experimentation were systematically channelled into relevant standardisation and coordination bodies, including 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) and SNS JU working groups, contributing to the alignment of TrialsNet results with emerging B5G requirements and evaluation frameworks. These activities, together with the exploitation and innovation actions derived from OC sub-projects, reinforced the sustainability, credibility and transferability of the project outcomes, as comprehensively documented in D6.3.

Finally, the positive assessment provided by the OC sub-projects, as this was collected through a dedicated feedback survey conducted by the consortium at the end of the implementation phase, confirms the usability, clarity and fairness of the adopted framework from the perspective of the participating third parties. This direct feedback validates the effectiveness of the monitoring, evaluation and support mechanisms and reinforces the value of the TrialsNet OC as a best-practice model. As such, the TrialsNet approach offers a mature and field-tested methodology that can be directly adopted or adapted by future European Union (EU) funded projects aiming to expand their ecosystem, validate innovative technologies at scale and ensure reliable governance through competitive Open Call funding schemes.

1 Introduction

The Work Package 7 (WP7), titled “Open Call and Support to Third Parties”, is responsible for the management of the project’s Open Call (OC) and to provide support to third parties in line with the project objectives and structure. In the context of WP7, the Task 7.2 (T7.2) “Open Call Launch, proposal Evaluation, and Grants Award”, is responsible for the promotion of the Open Call, encompassing various tools and channels, thorough evaluation of proposals, involving multiple steps including also external expert evaluations, as well as legal and administrative support for selected applicants.

This deliverable corresponds to T7.3 of WP7 and reports the activities done for the monitoring and evaluation of the performed activities during the implementation of the funded proposals which is organized as follows.

Section 2 outlines a timetable with an overview of the activities carried out in the context of TrialsNet Open Call, the obligations incurred by both the consortium and the participating third parties and the corresponding dates, deadlines and milestones corresponding to the active period of TrialsNet (M1-M36) and the Open Call sub-projects duration (M1-M12).

Section 3 thoroughly describes the overall monitoring and review framework that was defined and implemented by the consortium with the scope of not only evaluating the sub-projects but also providing significant and substantive assistance towards maximising the expected outcomes that would enrich the TrialsNet Use Cases.

Section 4 meticulously describes the mechanisms and the framework for the quantitative and qualitative evaluation of the activities done by the third parties as depicted in the submitted official documents.

Section 5 provides the full results of the evaluation of the sub-projects based on the frameworks described above. This presentation demonstrates the diligence that the consortium took in the thorough, rational and documented evaluation of the subprojects.

Section 6 provides relevant remarks related to TrialsNet Open Call in terms of deviations occurred during the implementation of T7.3, key lessons learned from the process and an evaluation of the entire process with the aim of further improving it so that it can serve as methodology model for projects wishing to develop a relevant evaluation framework for future Open Calls.

Finally, Section 7 present the conclusions of this deliverable, highlighting the main outcomes of the overall Open Call process and related considerations.

To keep the length of the document contained, this deliverable is complemented by Annex A, which specifically includes the template of the Final Report provided to the Open Call sub-projects. All the submitted Final Reports are available for reference in a [dedicated repository](#).

2 Timeframe of implemented activities

Table 1 presents the complete timeline of activities associated with the implementation of the TrialsNet Open Call, mapping both the consortium's activities and the sub-projects' milestones across the 12-month execution period. The table aligns the Open Call reference months (M1–M12) with the corresponding TrialsNet reference months (M1–M36), providing a unified chronological view of all major actions. It summarises the sequence of required submissions by the third parties, such as the Operational Plan (OP), Monthly Reports (MR), Mid-Term Report, and Final Report, alongside the consortium's review activities, payments, monitoring processes and evaluation cycles. This timeline serves as a synchronised roadmap that ensures consistent coordination between TrialsNet and the funded sub-projects, clarifies dependencies between deliverables and review stages and supports transparent tracking of progress throughout the entire Open Call duration.

Table 1. Timeframe of implemented activities.

Month	May 2024	June 2024	July 2024	Aug 2024	Sept 2024	Oct 2024	Nov 2024	Dec 2024	Jan 2025	Feb 2025	Mar 2025	Apr 2025	May 2025	June 2025	July 2025	Aug 2025	Sept 2025	Oct 2025	Nov 2025	Dec 2025
TrialsNet reference month	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
OC reference month	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12								
	Start					Mid-Term						End								
Sub-projects activities	OP submission	MR	MR	MR	MR	Mid-Term Report	MR	MR	MR	MR	MR	Final Report								
	Design																			
					Implementation															
								Trials and Data extraction												
TrialsNet OC activities	OP review	Initial payment	Monthly Reports Review			Mid-Term review – Review meetings – Communication of results			Monthly Reports Review			Final-Term review – Review meetings – Communication of results			Interim payment	OC data analysis and review		Final Payment		End of TrialsNet

3 Monitoring and review framework

The purpose of the consortium was to develop an assessment framework for third parties of the OC which would be able to examine the qualitative and quantitative fulfilment of the contractual terms and would offer valuable advice/guidance with a view to timely treatment of deviations. The official strategy that was followed is based on the logic that the TrialsNet project can benefit significantly from the contribution of the OC results and must therefore support them to maximise the expected results. The design and implementation methodology presented in this document is a true outcome of collaborative work between the technical, administrative and OC managing partners of TrialsNet.

Consequently, a periodic framework was established for the formal review of the documents submitted by the sub-projects based on the provision of the OC tender documents. The official review therefore refers to the formal documents reported in the third parties' contracts and which are required to be submitted within specific deadlines.

In addition, an informal evaluation plan was established on a monthly basis that would ensure the smooth conduction of activities and provide feedback to the third parties and to make sure these are in line with the project objectives. This included the submission of a monthly report in which, apart from the technical activities, a short self-assessment on the projected innovation was included. Sub-projects participating in Option 2: New use case(s) with the use of additional field trials infrastructures were also required to submit by end of September 2024 a description of the infrastructure intended to be utilised.

For the exchange of documents between the TrialsNet consortium and the OC third parties a dedicated directory was utilised using SharePoint [9], organised in subfolders for the administrative documents, the communication and dissemination activities, the scheduled meetings, the review processes and other useful material (e.g. TrialsNet logos, general documents, TrialsNet deliverables, templates, etc.).

3.1 Formal review

Table 2 provides an overview of the formal documents that each OC sub-project was contractually required to submit during its implementation period. These documents constitute the core elements of the official review process and enable the consortium to assess compliance with the agreed workplan, monitor progress and evaluate the achievement of technical objectives. The table lists the three mandatory reports as stated in the relevant contracts signed between CERTH and the third parties, the Operational Plan, the Mid-Term Report and the Final Report, together with their corresponding submission deadlines (expressed in reference to the OC sub-projects month. This structured reporting framework ensures consistent documentation across all sub-projects, supports transparent evaluation procedures and provides the necessary input for both mid-term corrective actions and final assessment of results.

Table 2. Formal documents required to be submitted by third parties.

Document	Deadline (corresponds to OC reference month)
Operational Plan	M1
Mid-term Report	M6
Final Report	M12

3.1.1 Operational Plan

This was the first official document required for submission encompassing specific topics and sections imperative to the project's success. As stipulated in the executed contract, this report was expected to be submitted within the OC M1 of the contractual period (May 2024). The Operational Plans were subjected to review by the TrialsNet consortium and updates to these plans were requested where deemed necessary. The review of these plans was carried out by the TrialsNet experts, without being compulsory, to identify potential weak points and to the benefit of the OC outcomes. The submission of the Operational Plan was a necessary requirement by the consortium for the advance payment corresponding to 20% of the financial objective of the submitted proposal.

All OC sub-projects responded with the timely submission of the Operation Plan according to the provisions of their contracts. The TrialsNet consortium performed a review of these plans and sent comments for potential improvements, mainly in the part concerning the implementation of the technical object and resubmission was requested for selected sub-projects, to ensure that a well-designed plan was in place.

3.1.2 Mid-Term review

Third parties participating in the OC submitted their mid-term review reporting documents by M6 of their activities, corresponding to M22 of TrialsNet project (end of October 2024). Requested documents were based on templates shared by the TrialsNet consortium and included the mid-term report of each sub-project, the report of the addressed KPIs and KVI (intended) and a documentation of the financial expenses carried out by the third parties. For the last month (M6), an estimation of the organisation's expenses was required in case the official expenses were not finalised. It should be noted that although the OC financial terms deploy a lump sum funding, the purpose was to conduct an informal check on whether the declared expenses are rationally distributed according to the Operational Plans submitted and the implemented activities reported for M6.

The mid-term report document filled out according to the following mandatory contents:

- **Use case definition:** A full description of the Use Case aspects of each sub-project, including the Use Case description, the addressed KPIs, KVIs and related requirements based on the provided Excel files by the consortium. The application design aspects should be reported in terms of architecture, modules, functionalities, interfaces, etc and describe the activities performed in terms of technical developments. Last, a trial and test description were required to provide information of the planned activities (location, dates and number of intended users to be engaged). Based on the above, a plan on how the users will be engaged should be reported.
- **Platform and Network solutions:** The infrastructure to be utilised for the technical solution should be reported (e.g. commercial by indicating the carrier and the type of the network or ad-hoc deployment) and a schematic figure of the equipment/ devices, communication mechanisms or cloud infrastructure. In addition, connectivity aspects, focusing on the network interface and the deployment areas including coverage area should be explained sufficiently.
- **First integration and testing activities:** Third parties reported necessary laboratory tests performed for defining the baseline performances, on-field tests and early demo with a report on any measured KPIs and KVIs.

The reports were requested to be submitted in .docx format document to facilitate the data extraction and integration to the TrialsNet project. After the submission of the mid-term reports, the TrialsNet consortium experts proceeded to the evaluation and assessment of the work done according to the evaluation framework presented in Section 4. A mid-term review virtual meeting also took place (see Section 3.2.2, third meeting) to gain a better understanding of the sub-projects achievements and allow for an open discussion about the expectations of the TrialsNet consortium from the projects and suggestions for improvements.

After the completion of the meetings, the relevant experts drafted an official review report document which was shared to the third parties along with an official letter for informing about the completion of the audit.

3.1.3 Final-Term review

In a similar organisation to the mid-term review, the final review took place after the completion of the sub-project's activities. The TrialsNet consortium requested the submission of a final report by M12 (end of April 2025). After the submission of the final reports, the third parties were requested to submit, before the end of the evaluation three (3) excel files regarding a) the KPIs validation, b) the report on KVIs raw data and c) the Trials management status which are used to import the raw data to the results of TrialsNet and a declaration of the expenses for this period as carried out for the mid-term review. For the completion of the final report a template was created and shared to the third parties presented in Annex A. Main aspects of the report include:

- **Use case final implementation:** A summary of the development activities that have been performed for the period, highlighting the main progresses towards the final trial phase and a description of the final application that has been developed in terms of functionalities with pictures of the graphical User Interface (GUI) to be provided.

- **Final infrastructure deployment:** This section should be completed only by the Option 2 sub-projects which made use of their own platforms and network solutions to run the trials. Descriptions include pictures of the actual deployment in the trial location site including devices used.
- **Trials and results:** Those were reported in two phases, the pre-trial and the actual trial phase with a detailed description of the trial that has been performed. All test and trial descriptions were requested to be aligned with the information provided in the three excel files. By extension, a detailed presentation in the document was included about the results such as the KPIs and KVI's measurement and validation.
- **Summary of the performed work:** In this short section, a comprehensive summary of the performed work (presented in tables) would report the main aspects described in the previous sections. In addition, each sub-project was required to report on the Innovation aspects and how this outlook has been enhanced after 12 months of development and trials. This should be linked with a report on the exploitation plan based on the work outcomes. Last, each sub-project reported in this section any deviations, positive or negative, to the performed activities and the mitigation plan/actions which has been put in place.

Before the submission of the final reports, the TrialsNet experts organised a webinar which took place on Wednesday, 12th of March 2024, between 13:00 to 15:00 hours CET to assist the third parties in the reporting process, followed by an open discussion to address questions or clarifications.

After the submission of the final reports, the TrialsNet consortium experts proceeded to the evaluation and assessment of the work done according to the evaluation framework presented in Section 4. A final review virtual meeting also took place (see Section 3.2.2, fourth meeting) to gain a better understanding of the sub-projects' achievements. Following the completion of the meetings, the relevant experts drafted an official review final evaluation report document which was shared to the third parties along with an official letter for informing about the completion of the audit and the brief outcomes.

3.1.4 Project-level integration of the final reports data

As part of T7.3, the final reports submitted by the OC sub-projects constituted a key input for the consolidation of technical and evaluation results at project level. The information collected through the final reports covering, among others, the description of the final system implementation, the trials setup and execution, network and application performance results, KPI measurements, KVI assessment, risk analysis and overall conclusions and lessons learned, was systematically reviewed by the consortium for integration in TrialsNet.

Use case specific information extracted from the final reports, such as final implementation descriptions, trial scenarios, network setup, performance results, and domain-specific observations, was incorporated into the domain-oriented deliverables D3.3 [5] (ITSS domain), D4.3 [6] (eHealth domain) and D5.3 [7] (CTE domain). In particular, the tables and narrative sections reporting trial descriptions and execution, measured KPIs, use case performance assessment, and added value brought by the OC sub-projects were reused to extend and reinforce the final presentation of use cases and large-scale trials in the corresponding domains. This ensured that OC results were fully integrated alongside core project activities, enabling a coherent and comprehensive representation of the validated use cases across all clusters and deployment contexts.

In parallel, cross-domain and transversal data extracted, such as consolidated KPI values, KVI evaluation results, trial metadata, quantitative and qualitative impact indicators and inputs relevant to dissemination, standardisation and exploitation were aggregated and harmonised for inclusion in WP6 activities as reported in D6.3 [8]. These data directly supported the final KPI and KVI assessment, comparative analysis between project and OC trials and the documentation of dissemination, standardisation and exploitation outcomes.

Through this structured and traceable reuse of the OC data, Task 7.3 ensured that the sub-project results were not treated as standalone outcomes, but were effectively embedded within the project's final technical, validation and impact deliverables, reinforcing the overall robustness, consistency and added value of the TrialsNet results.

3.2 Periodic informal review and monitoring of activities

Following extensive consultations among the members of the TrialsNet consortium, it was decided to implement, with the consent of the third parties, a mechanism for a unified and continuous monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of the projects. This mechanism along with the presented activities in this sub-section

constitute an informal activity as they are not included in the “hard” prerequisite measures based on contractual obligations. It is noted that such a monitoring mechanism was not foreseen even for the members of the TrialsNet consortium and while it was an extensive action which significantly increased the workload for those involved, it shows the importance given to assist the sub-projects to achieve results that will significantly enhance the impact of the project. The monthly reports (submitted by end of each month, unless it was an official review month) included a self-assessment on the project innovation.

Input for this monthly report was provided through a dedicated the template and the assigned TrialsNet experts review the information each month and provided their feedback by directly contacting the third parties through the helpdesk created and described in D7.2 [2]. When deemed necessary, a revision to this report was requested and/or a virtual meeting was scheduled between the TrialsNet experts and the sub-project parties.

3.2.1 Infrastructure description for Option 2 sub-projects

Sub-projects that stated their intention to utilize their own network infrastructure for the purposes of their Use Case (Option 2 – OC tender) were required to submit a complete description no later than 15 September 2024. This requirement was introduced to ensure that the technical characteristics, deployment conditions and capabilities of the additional infrastructures could be systematically assessed and formally incorporated into the project’s platforms and network documentation, enabling their inclusion and consolidation within WP2 deliverable D2.3 [3]. The infrastructure should be described in terms of platform and network solutions that would be used by the trial, with a schematic figure that would present the end-to-end interaction between the equipment and devices, the network solution (including communication mechanisms) and the platforms, such as cloud infrastructure, IoT or VR/XR platforms, etc.

3.2.2 Meetings and demonstration of the results

First, introductory virtual meeting was organised according to the TrialsNet domains of Infrastructure, Transport, Security & Safety (ITSS), which took place on Wednesday the 15th of September 2024. This meeting served as an opportunity for mutual introduction, enabling the third parties to present themselves and get informed about the outline of the intended organisation from the TrialsNet Consortium.

A **second** meeting requiring the physical participation of third parties was organised along with the 5th plenary meeting of the consortium in Turin. A dedicated session for the sub-projects was scheduled for the last day of the plenary, Friday the 21st of June 2024, encompassing within the agenda an introduction of the TrialsNet project, including objectives, expectations and results, a 10-15minutes presentation slot for each sub-project addressing pertinent topics and last, an open discussion with a Q&A session covering all aspects pertaining to the monitoring of the OC activities. In this meeting the consortium, represented by Promozione per l’Innovazione fra Industria e Università Associazione (PIIU) and Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH), also presented the details of the review framework to be followed in the next months, as described in this document, to ensure that all third parties are aware of the expectations, to clarify obscure points and of course to strengthen the feeling of fair and transparent treatment. Particular mention and instructions were also given on issues related to the obligations of sub-projects according to the OC terms, such as the treatment of ethical issues and the dissemination of activities. Furthermore, a presentation of the project deliverables was made with links to the official TrialsNet website where these can be found. These documents are perceived as the most important related to the OC framework and deemed as a good guidance for the third parties and an enabler for the good integration of the OC results to TrialsNet.

A **third** virtual meeting took place after the submission of the Mid-term report (OC M6) for each sub-project individually with the participation of the two review coordinators (see section 4). The meetings had a duration of two hours during which the third parties presented the Use Case usage, the infrastructure utilised, connectivity aspects, deployment areas, identified risks, the expected KPIs/ KVIs with the targeted impact on the TrialsNet project, an overview of the trials and tests planned or executed and side activities such as public/ user engagement, their performed innovation, etc. These meetings took place from Monday the 11th of November 2024 to Friday the 29th of November 2024 and were organised centrally by CERTH who provided the digital means.

Fourth and last meeting was organised in a similar way to the third one to facilitate the final review of the sub-projects (OC M12). The meetings had a duration of two hours with the participation of the two review coordinators and took place individually for each sub-project between Monday 19/05/2025 to Wednesday 04/06/2025.

The agenda included target topics concerning the contribution of the results to TrialsNet, including the final UCs and activities done, the final expected KPIs/ KVIIs and the tests/ trials executed together with the results of the user engagement. During the last part of the meeting a live demo of the trials was requested to be prepared and demonstrated. The parties received timely notice of this requirement, allowing UCs with constraints that prevented live demonstration to plan for video recordings during the actual trials, ensuring full documentation of the concept's implementation.

4 Evaluation and monitoring framework

In the context of T7.3, two mechanisms were established for the monitoring and the evaluation of the OC sub-project activities respectively. The aim was to create a team of competent experts under the guidance of the administrative responsible partners (CERTH, PIIU and TrialsNet management), in order to provide a valid and timely information regarding the activities of the OC.

Basic monitoring information, schedules and Event Log was maintained electronically via a master file located in cloud, which included the following information:

- Basic information of each sub-project (third parties included, coordinator, infrastructure option, site location, abstract, etc.)
- Evaluation experts
- Milestones for submitting official documents (Operational Plan, Mid-term review and Final review) and successful completion
- Monthly report records and comments issued by the TrialsNet experts which were then communicated to the third parties by the administration team
- Contact details of the sub-project third parties
- Event log for the communication between TrialsNet consortium and third parties (included the subject and aim for communication, the recipient and date)

4.1 Evaluation team

The evaluation team appointed by the consortium consists of 3 levels based on the scope of application that each member have:

- **Administrative Level:** This was common to all sub-projects as it should have a comprehensive overview of the actions being carried out. For this purpose, CERTH with the assistance of PIIU was appointed general administrator of the OC sub-projects.
- **Technical Level:** Each sub-project included a team of four (4) different technical experts. One was responsible for the platform and network solutions deployed, one was the Use Case leader (usually the respective TrialsNet WP leader) and two responsible for the KPIs and KVI monitoring respectively.
- **Innovation Level:** The Innovation Manager (Simon Fletcher) of TrialsNet was appointed responsible for monitoring and assisting the third parties in identifying deviations to their projected innovation.

Table 3 below shows the full evaluation team assigned to each sub-project.

Table 3. TrialsNet evaluation team of the OC sub-projects.

Sub-project Information				Evaluation Experts			
ID	Name	Site / Location	Option	Platform and Network solutions	Use Case (WP leader)	KPIs/KVIs	Innovation
#025	Connected Rails: Evaluating 5G for Autonomous Tram Operations	Florence	Option 2	Simone Bertucci (TEI)	Cristian Petrache (ORO)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)

#029	5G-enabled Secure Surveillance System (5GS3)	Athens	Option 2	Andreas Geor-gakopoulos (WINGS, Nikos Pappagianopoulos (AIA)	Cristian Petrache (ORO)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#030	SkyLink Vision	Madrid	Option 1a	Aruna Prem Bianzino (UC3M)	Cristian Petrache (ORO)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#062	CITY4ALL	Turin	Option 2	Gabriele Scivoletto (NXW)	Cristian Petrache (ORO)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#008	AI/ML-based Preventive and Reactive Emergency handling (AI-PREM-SET-MCX)	Iasi	Option 1a	Razvan Mihai (ORO)	Cristian Petrache (ORO)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#047	MILESTONE - A REAL-TIME AI-ENABLED WORKER SAFETY PRESERVATION SYSTEM	Athens	Option 1b	Andreas Georgeakopoulos (WINGS), Iliia Christanton i, Dimitra Tsakanika (DAEM)	Cristian Petrache (ORO)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#055	Automated Tele-Operated Sustainable (ATOS) driving	Antwerp	Option 2	Nina Slamnik Krijestorac (IMEC)	Cristian Petrache (ORO)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#045	Intelligent control of interconnected manufacturing infrastructures (i-CNC)	Peania, Patras	Option 2	Marco Gramaglia (UC3M)	Cristian Petrache (ORO)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)

#042	AdaptoFlow	Iasi	Option 1b	Razvan Mihai (ORO)	Cristian Petrache (ORO)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#026	AI4RTC: AI applications for Real-time Charging Load Management	Athens	Option 2	Andreas Georgakopoulos (WINGS)	Cristian Petrache (ORO)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#040	Cities Without Barriers	Turin	Option 2	Gabriele Scivoletto (NXW)	Cristian Petrache (ORO)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#027	COMO5: COntinuous MOnitoring of patients with chronic disease via 5G	Pisa	Option 1a	Paola Iovanna (TEI)	Andrea Di Giglio (TIM)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#043	META-CLINIC	Istanbul	Option 2	Marco Gramaglia (UC3M)	Andrea Di Giglio (TIM)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#009	MediVision-5G (eHealth)	Barcelona	Option 2	Aruna Prem Bianzino (UC3M)	Andrea Di Giglio (TIM)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#013	Remote Coordination and Interworking of First Responders in Emergency Situations	Madrid	Option 1a	Aruna Prem Bianzino (UC3M)	Andrea Di Giglio (TIM)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#017	5GVIREH: Virtual Reality Enhanced Rehabilitation	Rome	Option 2	Gabriele Scivoletto (NXW)	Andrea Di Giglio (TIM)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)

#028	Beyond 5G Football Stadium	Israel	Option 2	Marco Gramaglia (UC3M)	Albert Vidal Palma (TID)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#010	Tu-rin5Games	Turin	Option 2	Mauro Agus (TIM)	Albert Vidal Palma (TID)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#036	Torino 4U: 10 things to see around you	Turin	Option 2	Mauro Agus (TIM)	Albert Vidal Palma (TID)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#001	6GVision: Improvement of the 5G Open testbed at imec with vision-aided mmW gNB	Antwerp	Option 1b	Nina Slamnik Krijestorac (IMEC)	Albert Vidal Palma (TID)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#019	DREAM-PARK	Turin	Option 1b	Mauro Agus (TIM)	Albert Vidal Palma (TID)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#061	5G AUGMENTED REALITY TOUR FOR THE UNESCO SITE “HISTORICAL CENTER OF NAPLES”	Naples	Option 2	Gabriele Scivoletto (NXW)	Albert Vidal Palma (TID)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
#058	“Remember Ascari”: MR in MAUTO – Immersive MR Experience in F1 (MAUTO)	Turin	Option 2	Mauro Agus (TIM)	Albert Vidal Palma (TID)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)

#049	Mobile Augmented Reality for Outdoor PoI Enrichm.	Romania	Option 1a	Razvan Mihai (ORO)	Albert Vidal Palma (TID)	Paolo Giaccone (CNIT), Hassan Osman (RW)	Simon Fletcher (RW)
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4.2 Technical evaluation framework

For the purpose of evaluating the official progress of the OC sub-projects, TrialsNet developed and imposed an innovative and comprehensive methodology which applied in the mid-term and final review.

This methodology was based on FMEA [10], in which the evaluation criteria were equated with potential risks to the successful completion of the sub-projects through a specific score gradation risk impact as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Evaluation score gradation for impact assessment.

Severity Level	Score Number (from - to %)		Impact	Colour
Extremely Severe	0%	30%	Very limited implementation with no useful results	Red
Severe	30%	50%	Severe deviations with minimum output	Purple
Warning	50%	65%	Serious deviations with big impact on the quality	Orange
Alarming	65%	80%	Large deviations are in place with medium impact to the quality of results	Yellow
Moderate	80%	90%	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact	Blue
Insignificant	90%	100%	Excellent implementation or with small deviations	Green

For each of the two official evaluation processes (mid-term and final), the consortium jointly agreed on the criteria that will be used to reflect all the actions implemented by the subprojects. The criteria differ per review period as they had to be adapted to the gravity of the design in the first phase, while at the end of the OC sub-projects period attention was paid to the evaluation of the results, which are the main outcome of the sub-projects in the project.

The importance of this ranking for the overall score gradation of the projects is of great importance, as it reflects the quality and the extent of implementation of the technical objective. Through workshops held within the consortium, it was decided the way each criterion should be evaluated, which would imply that sub-projects receiving a score of less than 85% (i.e. a lower medium level of implementation quality), should be thoroughly examined for failures to implement parts of their contractual obligations. For small score deviations (overall score above 85%) which are of course expected, it was decided that concern only small deviations in quality which do not reflect a failure to implement one or more technical objectives.

For the mid-term review phase, in which the criteria differed from those related to their contractual obligations (final review), a poor rating meant the initiation of direct discussions with the related sub-projects in order to identify the causes, the associated risks that arise and through appropriate mitigation actions, to provide them with additional assistance to address these in the continuation of their activities. For the final review phase, a poor scoring would mean the omission of technical objective, and the mechanism for reducing the relative funding of the sub-projects should be activated according to the declaration documents of the OC tender.

4.2.1 Criteria for mid-term evaluation

Table 5 presents the set of evaluation criteria applied during the mid-term review of the OC sub-projects, along with their corresponding weights. These criteria were designed to provide a balanced assessment of each sub-project's progress during the first half of the implementation, focusing on four equally important dimensions: technical implementation, trials or tests planned or conducted, relevance, the expected impact of the KPIs/KVIs and the level of innovation demonstrated. By assigning an equal weighting of 25% to each criterion, the consortium ensured that the mid-term evaluation reflected not only technical execution but also preparedness for upcoming trials, alignment with measurable project outcomes and the innovative character of the work.

Table 5. Mid-term evaluation criteria.

No.	Criterion	Weight in percentage
1	Technical implementation	25%
2	Trials or Tests planned/ conducted	25%
3	KPIs/KVIs relevance and impact	25%
4	Innovation	25%

For the first phase, the criteria had equal weighting and according to the score assigned by the evaluation team to each one, an overall percentage score was formed (best of 100%).

4.2.2 Criteria for the final term evaluation

Table 6 outlines the evaluation criteria applied during the final-term review of the OC sub-projects, together with their respective weightings, which were adjusted to reflect the increased emphasis on results and measurable impact at the end of the implementation period. Unlike the mid-term review, the final assessment prioritised the successful execution of the technical objectives and the quality and completeness of the conducted trials, assigning each of these criteria a weight of 35%. The measurement and validation of KPIs and KVIs, central indicators of the sub-projects' contribution to the overall TrialsNet objectives, were weighted at 20% and 10% respectively. Collectively, these criteria enabled a rigorous, transparent, and outcome-oriented assessment of each sub-project's achievements and compliance with contractual obligations.

Table 6. Final term evaluation criteria.

No.	Criterion	Weight in percentage
1	Technical implementation	35%
2	Conducted trials	35%
3	KPIs measurement and evaluation	20%
4	KVIs measurement and evaluation	10%

For the final phase, the criteria had the weighting shown in Table 6 to better reflect the impact of the respective results to the TrialsNet and according to the score assigned by the evaluation team to each one, an overall percentage score was once again formed (best of 100%).

4.3 Evaluation process

All OC sub-projects submitted their reports in time based on their contractual obligation in each review phase. After the submission of their reports, CERTH was responsible to collect all the input, organize it in the cloud in separate review folders for each sub-project and informed the evaluation team. The evaluation team provided their feedback and submitted it in the cloud along with questions towards the third parties. Their feedback included a first evaluation recommendation for the four criteria applied in each phase.

After the first draft evaluation of the submitted documents, CERTH as the lead administrator, organized virtual meetings to be held between the third parties and a team of two review coordinators set by the consortium. The use of separate coordinators for the review meetings was done as it was deemed impossible for some technical experts to participate in all the meetings. Furthermore, by dividing the workload, better control and monitoring was possible. Thus, the obligation of these two coordinators was to transfer all the comments of the evaluation team to the sub-projects through the virtual meetings and then to convey the feedback in a concise manner back to the competent technical experts in order to arrive at the final score.

In the end of this evaluation process, these coordinators had a subsidiary role. To compile the document of the report to third parties, with which they would provide them with an analytical presentation of the evaluation feedback per each thematic topic and transfer the overall score of the sub-project to the evaluation tool designed for this purpose and which would present their ranking based on the scoring gradation presented in Section 4.2.

A step-by-step overview of the review process is presented in Table 7. This process is initiated at the end of the respective deadline month of each review phase and shows responsible entity either from the TrialsNet consortium or the sub-projects to take the corresponding actions.

Table 7. Evaluation review steps.

Activity	Who
Official report (mid-term and final term)	Third Parties
Prepare evaluation folder and inform Review coordinators	CERTH
Send to the Technical experts and coordinate feedback	Review Coordinators Meeting Participant 1 & 2
Review mid-term report input and provide feedback + evaluation recommendation on Review Report	Technical Experts
Compile final Review Report + assign evaluation score	Review Coordinators
Consent and finalize documents	Review Coordinators / Technical Experts

5 Review results and consequent actions

In previous sections the process of the review and the evaluation of the work done by the sub-projects is extensively described. In this chapter the evaluation results are presented for each review phase carried out. For this, a tool implemented within excel worksheets was developed which takes as input the score assigned to each sub-project for all the criteria and calculates, based on their weight, an overall score. It then interpolates these scores with the values defined as “performance limits” by the score gradation defined in Table 4 and returns as output the evaluation risk significance and the expected impact as defined by the consortium.

5.1 Mid-term evaluation results

Table 8 below presents the mid-term evaluation results for all sub-projects. As mentioned in section 4, the evaluation criteria for the mid-term did not correspond to the “hard” contractual obligations defined by the OC tender documents, since the consortium wished to broaden the review field and include multiple parameters which demonstrate the degree of maturity in the implementation planning of the sub-projects.

The table applies a colour-coded grading scale, derived from the FMEA [10] inspired scoring methodology, to indicate the degree of implementation risk associated with each sub-project. Scores above 90% are marked in green and classified as *Insignificant risk*, meaning that the project demonstrates excellent implementation with only minor deviations. Scores between 80% and 90% fall into the blue category, labelled *Moderate risk*, indicating medium-level deviations that do not threaten the overall execution but may require monitoring. Lower score ranges trigger more concerning classifications: yellow for *Alarming risk* (65–80%), purple for *Severe risk* (30–50%), and red for *Extremely Severe risk* (0–30%), each signalling increasing levels of deviation and potential impact on the project’s expected outcomes. This structured colour-and-risk scheme enables evaluators to quickly identify sub-projects that may require additional support, targeted mitigation actions, or closer follow-up in the subsequent phase of implementation.

Table 8. OC sub-projects mid-term evaluation score.

No.	Sub-project - ID	Sub-project name	Criterion 1: Technical implementation	Criterion 2: Trials or Tests planned/ conducted	Criterion 3: KPIs/KV Is relevance and impact	Criterion 4: Innovation	Evaluation score (%)	Evaluation's risk significance	Evaluation impact
1	#025	Connected Rails: Evaluating 5G for Autonomous Tram Operations	9	9	9	8	87,50%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact
2	#029	5G-enabled Secure Surveillance System (5GS3)	9	7	7	9	80,00%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact
3	#030	SkyLink Vision	10	9	7	9	87,50%	Moderate	Medium deviations to

									the implementation and impact
4	#062	CITY4ALL	9	8	9	8	85,00%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact
5	#008	AI/ML-based Preventive and Reactive Emergency handling (AI-PREM-SET-MCX)	9	8	8	10	87,50%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact
6	#047	MILESTONE - A REAL-TIME AI-ENABLED WORKER SAFETY PRESERVATION SYSTEM	8	7	8	9	80,00%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact
7	#055	Automated Tele-Operated Sustainable (ATOS) driving	10	10	8	9	92,50%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
8	#045	Intelligent control of interconnected manufacturing infrastructures (i-CNC)	9	8	5	9	77,50%	Alarming	Large deviations are in place with medium impact to the quality of results
9	#042	Adap-toFlow	9	7	8	10	85,00%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the im-

									plementation and impact
10	#026	AI4RTC: AI applications for Real-time Charging Load Management	9	9	7	9	85,00%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact
11	#040	Cities Without Barriers	9	9	8	9	87,50%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact
12	#027	COMO5: Continuous Monitoring of patients with chronic disease via 5G	8	9	7	9	82,50%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact
13	#043	META-CLINIC	10	9	8	9	90,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
14	#009	Medi-Vision-5G (eHealth)	8	7	6	8	72,50%	Alarming	Large deviations are in place with medium impact to the quality of results
15	#013	Remote Coordination and Interworking of First Responders in Emergency Situations	9	9	7	9	85,00%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact

16	#017	5GVIREH: Virtual Reality Enhanced Rehabilitation	9	9	7	10	87,50%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact
17	#028	Beyond 5G Football Stadium	9	8	8	10	87,50%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact
18	#010	Turin5Games	8	8	9	10	87,50%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact
19	#036	Torino 4U: 10 things to see around you	9	10	8	10	92,50%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
20	#001	6GVision: Improvement of the 5G Open testbed at imec with vision-aided mmW gNB	10	9	8	10	92,50%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
21	#019	DREAM-PARK	4	2	4	6	40,00%	Severe	Severe deviations with minimum output
22	#061	5G AUGMENTED REALITY TOUR FOR THE UNESCO SITE	9	9	7	10	87,50%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact

		“HISTORICAL CENTER OF NAPLES”							
23	#058	“Remember Ascari”: MR in MAUTO – Immersive MR Experience in F1 (MAUTO)	6	10	4	9	72,50%	Alarming	Large deviations are in place with medium impact to the quality of results
24	#049	Mobile Augmented Reality for Outdoor PoI Enrichment	10	10	8	10	95,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations

The following graph in Figure 1 presents an overview of the scores received by the sub-projects in **ranking order**. It provides a visual representation of the mid-term evaluation scores of all sub-projects, displayed in ranking order from highest to lowest performance. The diagram illustrates the overall percentage score each sub-project achieved based on the four equally weighted mid-term evaluation criteria, enabling an immediate comparison of their relative progress at the halfway point of implementation. The figure also highlights the distribution of risk significance levels associated with the scores, reflecting the colour-coded gradation defined in the evaluation framework.

Figure 1. OC sub-projects mid-term evaluation scores in ranking order.

As seen in Figure 1 above and Table 9 below, four sub-projects (circled in red above) received comparatively low scores, indicating an increased level of implementation risk. These cases were flagged within the evaluation framework and triggered enhanced monitoring measures. In response, and with the objective of actively supporting the third parties, the TrialsNet consortium promptly organised dedicated virtual meetings with the corresponding sub-project teams to identify the underlying causes of the observed risks and to jointly define and agree on appropriate mitigation actions, thereby facilitating corrective measures and ensuring the successful continuation of the sub-project activities.

Table 9. Mid-term review overall risk gradation representation.

Risk gradation index	Overall representation	Percentage of the total
Extremely Severe	0	0,00%
Severe	1	4,17%
Warning	0	0,00%
Alarming	3	12,50%
Moderate	15	62,50%
Insignificant	5	20,83%
	24	100 %

5.2 Final-term evaluation results

Table 10 below presents the evaluation results of all sub-projects for the final term. In this phase, the evaluation criteria for the did correspond to the “hard” contractual obligations defined by the OC tender documents, as it was also the consortium's obligation to properly evaluate these obligations and to determine if full funding should be provided to the sub-projects or whether any anticipated reduced performance clauses should be triggered.

Table 10. OC sub-projects final-term evaluation scores.

No.	Sub-project - ID	Sub-project name	Criterion 1: Technical implementation	Criterion 2: Trials or Tests planned/ conducted	Criterion 3: KPIs/KV Is relevance and impact	Criterion 4: Innovation	Evaluation score (%)	Evaluation's risk significance	Evaluation impact
1	#025	Connected Rails: Evaluating 5G for Autonomous Tram Operations	9	10	10	9	95,50%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
2	#029	5G-enabled Secure Surveillance System (5GS3)	9	9	10	8	91,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
3	#030	SkyLink Vision	10	9	8	8	90,50%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with

									small deviations
4	#062	CITY4ALL	9	9	9	9	90,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
5	#008	AI/ML-based Preventive and Reactive Emergency handling (AI-PRE-SET-MCX)	10	10	10	9	99,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
6	#047	MILESTONE - A REAL-TIME AI-ENABLED WORKER SAFETY PRESERVATION SYSTEM	10	10	10	9	99,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
7	#055	Automated Tele-Operated Sustainable (ATOS) driving	10	10	7	7	91,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
8	#045	Intelligent control of interconnected manufacturing infrastructures (i-CNC)	10	10	9	8	96,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
9	#042	Adap-toFlow	10	9	8	8	90,50%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations

10	#026	AI4RTC: AI applications for Real-time Charging Load Management	10	10	10	9	99,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
11	#040	Cities Without Barriers	9	10	10	7	93,50%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
12	#027	COMO5: Continuous Monitoring of patients with chronic disease via 5G	10	9	10	7	93,50%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
13	#043	META-CLINIC	10	9	10	8	94,50%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
14	#009	Medi-Vision-5G (eHealth)	10	10	10	10	100,00 %	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
15	#013	Remote Coordination and Interworking of First Responders in Emergency Situations	10	10	9	10	98,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
16	#017	5GVIREH: Virtual Reality Enhanced Rehabilitation	10	10	8	8	94,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with

									small deviations
17	#028	Beyond 5G Football Stadium	10	10	10	8	98,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
18	#010	Turin5Games	10	10	10	10	100,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
19	#036	Torino 4U: 10 things to see around you	10	10	9	10	98,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
20	#001	6GVision: Improvement of the 5GOpen testbed at imec with vision-aided mmW gNB	10	9	10	8	94,50%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
21	#019	DREAM-PARK	10	10	8	10	96,00%	Insignificant	Excellent implementation or with small deviations
22	#061	5G AUGMENTED REALITY TOUR FOR THE UNESCO SITE "HISTORICAL CENTER	10	9	8	7	89,50%	Moderate	Medium deviations to the implementation and impact

		OF NA- PLES”							
23	#058	“Remember As- cari”: MR in MAUTO – Immersive MR Experience in F1 (MAUTO)	10	10	8	10	96,00%	Insig- nifi- cant	Excellent imple- mentation or with small de- viations
24	#049	Mobile Augmented Reality for Outdoor PoI Enrich- ment	10	10	9	9	97,00%	Insig- nifi- cant	Excellent imple- mentation or with small de- viations

The following graph in Figure 2 presents an overview of the scores received by the sub-projects in **ranking order**. It illustrates the final-term evaluation scores of all sub-projects, ranked from highest to lowest, providing a clear overview of their performance at the conclusion of the implementation period. Each bar reflects the aggregated percentage score derived from the four weighted final evaluation criteria, with particular emphasis on technical implementation quality, execution of trials, and validated KPIs/KVIs measurements. The figure visually demonstrates the strong overall performance achieved across the sub-projects, with the vast majority of sub-projects falling within the highest scoring range and classified under the *Insignificant risk* category according to the colour-coded grading scale.

Figure 2. OC sub-projects final-term evaluation scores in ranking order.

As seen in Figure 2 above and Table 11 below, all sub-projects performed exceptionally well. This graphical representation enables an immediate understanding of the consistency and maturity of the delivered results and highlights the successful mitigation of earlier deviations identified in the mid-term review. As such, Figure 2 provides an effective summary of the final evaluation outcomes and supports the consortium’s conclusion that all sub-projects fulfilled their technical and contractual obligations to a high standard.

Table 11. Final-term review overall risk gradation representation.

Risk gradation index	Overall representation	Percentage of the total
Extremely Severe	0	0,00%
Severe	0	0,00%
Warning	0	0,00%
Alarming	0	0,00%
Moderate	1	4,17%
Insignificant	23	95,83%
	24	100 %

This overall good performance indication was expected from the consortium's side, as the monthly progress reports had shown the good quality of work being done by the sub-projects. Furthermore, the sub-projects which had a worse score within the first half of the period, the parts that required correction by the third parties or due to inadvertent presentation errors led to confusion among the technical experts of the consortium were fully identified and corrected.

Based on the above performance, the TrialsNet consortium concluded that all sub-projects have successfully completed their overall technical objectives while recorded the minor quality deviations that each one presented. This paved the way for the full compensation of the subprojects by the treasurer of the consortium (CERTH) according to the funding approved during the evaluation of the proposals.

5.3 Allocation of grants

Following the successful outcome for all participating sub-projects activities, CERTH as the acting treasurer of the TrialsNet consortium proceeded to the payment of grants based on the timeline presented in section 2 and the revised plan included in the contracts between CERTH and the third parties (see Section 6.1).

Table 12. Grants allocated based on payment plan.

No.	Sub-project ID	Sub-project name	Pre-financing Advance payment 20%	Final Budget after evaluation	Interim M12 (65%) Payment	Final Payment after review (15%)
1	#025	Connected Rails: Evaluating 5G for Autonomous Tram Operations	59.278,60 €	296.393,00 €	192.655,45 €	44.458,95 €
2	#029	5G-enabled Secure Surveillance System (5GS3)	59.450,00 €	297.250,00 €	193.212,50 €	44.587,50 €
3	#030	SkyLink Vision	39.850,00 €	199.250,00 €	129.512,50 €	29.887,50 €
4	#062	CITY4ALL	59.625,00 €	298.125,00 €	193.781,25 €	44.718,75 €

5	#008	AI/ML-based Preventive and Reactive Emergency handling (AI-PREMSET-MCX)	40.000,00 €	200.000,00 €	130.000,00 €	30.000,00 €
6	#047	MILESTONE - A REAL-TIME AI-ENABLED WORKER SAFETY PRESERVATION SYSTEM	40.000,00 €	200.000,00 €	130.000,00 €	30.000,00 €
7	#055	Automated Tele-Operated Sustainable (ATOS) driving	60.000,00 €	300.000,00 €	195.000,00 €	45.000,00 €
8	#045	Intelligent control of interconnected manufacturing infrastructures (i-CNC)	57.050,00 €	285.250,00 €	185.412,50 €	42.787,50 €
9	#042	AdaptoFlow	39.987,60 €	199.938,00 €	129.959,70 €	29.990,70 €
10	#026	AI4RTC: AI applications for Real-time Charging Load Management	39.962,50 €	199.812,50 €	129.878,13 €	29.971,88 €
11	#040	Cities Without Barriers	40.000,00 €	200.000,00 €	130.000,00 €	30.000,00 €
12	#027	COMO5: Continuous Monitoring of patients with chronic disease via 5G	38.000,00 €	190.000,00 €	123.500,00 €	28.500,00 €
13	#043	METACLINIC	55.250,00 €	276.250,00 €	179.562,50 €	41.437,50 €
14	#009	MediVision-5G (eHealth)	58.218,75 €	291.093,75 €	189.210,94 €	43.664,06 €
15	#013	Remote Coordination and Interworking of First Responders in Emergency Situations	40.000,00 €	200.000,00 €	130.000,00 €	30.000,00 €
16	#017	5GVIREH: Virtual Reality Enhanced Rehabilitation	38.330,00 €	191.650,00 €	124.572,50 €	28.747,50 €
17	#028	Beyond 5G Football Stadium	40.000,00 €	200.000,00 €	130.000,00 €	30.000,00 €

18	#010	Turin5Games	40.000,00 €	200.000,00 €	130.000,00 €	30.000,00 €
19	#036	Torino 4U: 10 things to see around you	40.000,00 €	200.000,00 €	130.000,00 €	30.000,00 €
20	#001	6G Vision: Improvement of the 5G Open testbed at imec with vision-aided mmW gNB	40.000,00 €	200.000,00 €	130.000,00 €	30.000,00 €
21	#019	DREAMPARK	39.460,00 €	197.300,00 €	128.245,00 €	29.595,00 €
22	#061	5G AUGMENTED REALITY TOUR FOR THE UNESCO SITE "HISTORICAL CENTER OF NAPLES"	39.787,60 €	198.938,00 €	129.309,70 €	29.840,70 €
23	#058	"Remember Ascari": MR in MAUTO – Immersive MR Experience in F1 (MAUTO)	60.000,00 €	300.000,00 €	195.000,00 €	45.000,00 €
24	#049	Mobile Augmented Reality for Outdoor PoI Enrichment	39.971,40 €	199.857,00 €	129.907,05 €	29.978,55 €
			1.104.221,45 €	5.521.107,25 €	3.588.719,71 €	828.166,09 €

The detailed payments made are reflected in the financial data submitted by the treasurer towards the European Commission (EC) at the end of TrialsNet project.

6 Remarks on the TrialsNet Open Call

This section provides a comprehensive reflection on the implementation of the TrialsNet OC, summarising the key points derived from the monitoring and evaluation activities, the deviations encountered throughout the process, and the lessons learned that can inform future Open Call frameworks. It also includes an assessment of the methodologies applied, incorporating direct feedback from participating third parties to validate the transparency, effectiveness and usability of the evaluation and support mechanisms. This section consolidates the overall insights gained during the execution of T7.3 and highlights opportunities for further refinement and replication of the TrialsNet approach in future R&I initiatives.

6.1 Deviations and lessons learned

Although a small number of procedural and technical deviations occurred, mainly related to interpretation of criteria, contractual adjustments and submission platform issues, the consortium addressed them effectively through additional clarification processes, revision of procedures and open communication with applicants. These deviations did not compromise the integrity, fairness or completeness of the evaluation outcomes and contributed valuable input for future improvements.

6.1.1 Harmonization of the evaluation criteria

Evaluators and experts within the TrialsNet consortium occasionally applied different interpretations of impact and feasibility indicators. This required additional clarification rounds and consensus meetings to harmonize assessments and although a detailed evaluation methodology was developed to tackle this issue, if such a methodology would have already been provided by the EC or at least if precise guideline were in place, it would have facilitated the evaluation of OC sub-projects and also enhance transparency.

6.1.2 Contracts review between CERTH and OC third parties

The initial funding plan based on the declaration of the OC, included the following payment scheme:

- **20%** of the assigned Grant after 1 month from the Grant signature against presentation of a detailed plan of activities,
- **65%** at completion of the contracted activities,
- **15%** when the EC accepts the project's final results.

Although the consortium repeatedly expressed its full availability to facilitate an audit of the documents and methodologies used, despite the absence of central instructions or recommendations from the EC, such an audit was ultimately not foreseen within the programme framework and requests were rejected. As a complication, the above conditions could no longer have been met.

Based on the EC's response, it was therefore decided to mitigate this issue by holding an open consultation with the sub-projects, were jointly agreed to revise our contracts, in order to replace the EC's audit by a final approval from the consortium, which would be validated through a dedicated General Assembly convergence. This activity resulted in an agreement with the third parties and was successfully completed before the expiration of the active contracts.

6.1.3 Lessons learned

The implementation of the Open Call demonstrated the importance of strong guidance, structured support mechanisms, and continuous coordination between the consortium and the selected third parties. Several lessons emerged throughout the process that can improve future Open Calls and enhance efficiency, transparency, and participation experience. In the following the most relevant lessons learned are summarized:

- **Need for clearer and more detailed guidance documents:** While templates and instructions were effective, further clarification of specific evaluation expectations and stronger alignment between templates and eligibility requirements would simplify preparation for applicants and increase consistency in evaluation.

- **Further refinement of communication channels:** Frequent updates, a structured helpdesk and an extensive FAQ proved valuable for applicants. Scaling these support services earlier in the process could further minimize misunderstandings and reduce information requests.
- **Continuous calibration between evaluators:** Regular meetings among evaluators were essential in achieving common interpretations of criteria. Institutionalizing such calibration as a mandatory step would streamline decision-making and reduce discrepancies in scoring.
- **Improvements to submission and reporting tools:** Technical issues experienced by a limited number of applicants highlighted the value of additional robustness in submission and documentation platforms, especially close to key deadlines.

These lessons form a solid basis for refining future Open Calls and ensure that the methodology remains adaptable, transparent and efficient as its use expands.

In addition to the above, an important lesson learned during the implementation of the TrialsNet OC was the added value of active participation in the SNS JU Open Call Task Force. Continuous exchange of information and coordination with other SNS JU projects enabled the consortium to maintain awareness of parallel OC initiatives and funded activities, thereby reducing the risk of overlaps and effectively preventing cases of double funding. This coordination mechanism proved essential for ensuring complementarity between projects, safeguarding the efficient use of public funding and reinforcing transparency and coherence across SNS JU OC schemes.

6.2 Assessment of the framework and methodologies

To ensure the robustness and long-term relevance of the TrialsNet Open Call framework developed within the project, an internal assessment was conducted among the participating third parties. This process was implemented through structured online evaluation forms designed to capture both qualitative and quantitative feedback on the methodologies applied and the organisational level provided. By actively involving the stakeholders who directly experienced the TrialsNet OC cycle, the consortium demonstrated a strong commitment to continuous improvement and accountability. This exercise reflects the consortium's dedication to maintaining high-quality standards and to positioning the methodologies used as reference models that can inform and guide future initiatives. Ultimately, the assessment not only strengthened the scientific and operational foundations of the Open Call process but also showcased its potential to evolve into a best-practice standard for subsequent projects wishing to adopt similar mechanisms.

The results of the assessment of the TrialsNet methodologies for the OC were overwhelmingly positive, confirming the effectiveness and maturity of the OC framework. Participants in the OC reported high levels of clarity, transparency and fairness throughout the process, acknowledging that the evaluation methods were well-structured, comprehensible and aligned with the objectives of the programme. The majority of respondents expressed confidence in the quality of the selection procedures and emphasized that the supporting tools, documentation and communication channels significantly facilitated their engagement. These positive outcomes validate the robustness of our approach and reinforce the project's ambition to set new standards for future Open Call implementations.

7 Conclusions

The implementation of the TrialsNet OC represented a significant achievement for the consortium, showcasing the effectiveness of a complex, multi-layered evaluation and monitoring framework that successfully guided 24 diverse sub-projects from concept to completion. All sub-projects delivered their planned activities within the designated timeframe and the trials conducted across multiple domains: Infrastructure, Transport, Security & Safety, eHealth, Emergency, Culture, Tourism, and Entertainment and were executed with high quality and strong alignment to the overarching objectives of the TrialsNet project. The performance results derived from the trials provide clear evidence of the robustness and maturity of the implemented solutions. KPI measurements demonstrated that the majority of technical targets were fully met or even exceeded, while the KVI outcomes revealed substantial added value in terms of user experience, societal benefit, innovation potential, and scalability. Collectively, these results validate the OC's contribution to expanding and enriching the TrialsNet ecosystem with impactful, data-driven and application-oriented insights.

Delivering these outcomes the consortium required to manage a highly complex technical, administrative and organisational process. The OC framework introduced by TrialsNet involved multiple formal and informal monitoring layers, recurring reporting obligations, rigorous mid-term and final evaluations, continuous communication with third parties and a structured, risk-based scoring methodology. Despite this inherent complexity, the process was implemented successfully and efficiently. The consortium ensured fairness, transparency and methodological consistency across all interactions, supported by a strong technical evaluation team, coordinated review phases, and well-defined procedures.

Following this robust demonstration of success, the OC evaluation framework demonstrated its effectiveness in assessing a diverse portfolio of proposals and selecting high-quality projects aligned with the programme objectives. While minor deviations occurred, they were managed efficiently and did not jeopardize the transparency or integrity of the evaluation. This success is reflected on the deviations encountered during the execution of the OC, along with the mitigation measures applied. These insights, presented in the preceding subsections, offer valuable guidance for refining future OC procedures and ensuring even greater efficiency, uniformity and impact in similar R&I initiatives.

The lessons learned highlight opportunities for increased process efficiency, clearer communication, and more precise evaluation criteria. Building upon these findings, future Open Calls can benefit from i) improved evaluator guidance and calibration, ii) increased automated eligibility checks, iii) enhanced submission and review support tools, and iv) stronger alignment between expected outcomes and project criteria.

In summary, the evaluation framework successfully fulfilled its intended purpose and provided a replicable and scalable methodology for future project selection processes within the Open Call framework.

Overall, the TrialsNet Open Call stands as a fully successful endeavour, achieving technical excellence, organisational coherence and positive participant experience. It provides a comprehensive, field-tested methodology that can serve as a reference model for forthcoming projects aiming to integrate third-party innovation, expand trial activities and strengthen the European 5G/B5G research landscape.

Acknowledgment

TrialsNet project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon-JU-SNS-2022 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101095871.

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- [3] TrialsNet Deliverable D2.3, "Final design of Platforms and Networks solutions", 17 December 2024
- [4] TrialsNet Deliverable D2.4, "Final Platforms and Networks solutions integration and deployments", 14 July 2025
- [5] TrialsNet Deliverable D3.3, "Use Cases final implementation and trials results for ITSS domain", 30 September 2025
- [6] TrialsNet Deliverable D4.3, "Use Cases final implementation and trials results for eHE domain", 30 September 2025
- [7] TrialsNet Deliverable D5.3, "Use Cases final implementation and trials results for CTE domain", 30 September 2025
- [8] TrialsNet Deliverable D6.3, "Final report on validation and dissemination", 24 December 2025
- [9] Microsoft Corporation, *SharePoint - Collaboration and Document Management Platform*.
<https://www.microsoft.com/sharepoint>
- [10] International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), "IEC 60812:2018 - Failure modes and effects analysis", Geneva, 2018

Annex A - Template of the Final Report

In the following, the template of the Final Report provided to the sub-projects is attached.

Co-funded by
the European Union

TrialsNet: TRials supported by Smart Networks beyond 5G

[Sub-project Name]

Final Report

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1 Introduction (1 page)

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TrialsNet

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- **Item 1:** Description of item 1
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3 Use Case final implementation

Add a short introductory text.

3.1 Development activities (1 page)

Provide a summary of the development activities that have been performed since what reported during the mid-term report, highlighting the main progresses towards the final trial phase.

3.2 Final application overview (2 pages)

Describe the final application that has been developed in terms of main functionalities, software, employed technologies, etc. Pictures of the GUI shall be provided.

4 Final infrastructure deployment (2 pages)

NOTE: This section shall be completed only by the following Option 2 sub-projects:

- AI4RTC: AI applications for Realtime Charging Load Management,
- 5G-enabled Secure Surveillance System (5GS3),
- Automated Tele-Operated Sustainable (ATOS) driving,
- Beyond 5G Foot-ball Stadium,
- Connected Rails: Evaluating 5G for Autonomous Tram Operations,
- MediVision-5G (eHealth),
- METACLINIC.

Describe the final infrastructure in terms of platforms and network solutions (including device connectivity aspects) that has been deployed to run the trial. Include also pictures of the actual deployment in the trial location site, including used devices.

5 Trials and results

Add a short introductory text.

5.1 Pre-trial activities (1 page)

Report the most relevant activities in terms of tests performed (in laboratory and/or on-filed) prior to the trial. Results in terms of KPIs measurements shall be also reported.

IMPORTANT: Test measurements results **shall be aligned** with the data provided in [TrialsNet-KPI-validation-Open-Call.xlsx](#).

Table 3. Test measurements results.

Test ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
ID	KPIs and related requirements (i.e., value do be met)	Measured value for each KPI	Very short summary of the outcome (e.g., validated, not validated (why?), main issues, etc.)

5.2 Trial description (from 2 to 3 pages)

Report a detailed description of the trial that has been performed, providing information on the following aspects:

- How the trial is denoted as “large-scale” in terms of, e.g., coverage, number of end users, length (e.g., days, number of sessions, etc.), data collected, etc.
- How the technologies and applications of the use case have been implemented in the trial,
- How the end users have been identified and selected, including users’ type, age target, etc.
- How verticals (e.g., municipalities, museums, industries, etc.) have been involved
- Provide information about the trial location, dates, etc.
- Provide a high-level storyline of the performed trial,
- Provide an assessment of the replicability of the trial,
- Report other aspects that are considered relevant.

Pictures of the performed trial shall be also included.

IMPORTANT: Trial description **shall be aligned** with the information provided in [TrialsNet-Trials-Management-Status-Open-Call.xlsx](#).

5.3 Trial execution and results

Add a short introductory text.

5.3.1 KPIs measurement and validation (from 2 to 3 pages)

Report about the performed KPIs measurements during the trial and related validation. Short explanation of the measurement methodology **shall be** reported. Relevant graph to support the results can be also included.

IMPORTANT: Trial measurements results **shall be aligned** with the data provided in [TrialsNet-KPI-validation-Open-Call.xlsx](#).

Table 4. Trial measurements results.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
ID	KPIs and related requirements (i.e., value do be met)	Measured value for each KPI	Very short summary of the outcome (e.g., validated, not validated (why?), main issues, etc.)

5.3.2 KVIs measurement and validation (from 2 to 3 pages)

Report about the KVs addressed and measured KVIs through users' questionnaire (which can be added as Annex of the document). Evaluation of the most relevant KVIs shall be also reported through graphs, etc.

IMPORTANT: Between the various KVs (and related measured KVIs) addressed during the trial, alignment with the data provided in [TrialsNet-KVI_raw_data_Open-Call.xlsx](#) shall be guaranteed.

6 Summary of the performed work

Add a short introductory text.

Table 5. Use Case description.

Use Case description
Report in maximum 15 lines the description of the Use Case.

Table 6. Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
Report in maximum 15 lines the description of the developed application including the employed technologies

Table 7. Trial activity.

Trial activity
Report in maximum 15 lines the performed trial activity in terms of location, involved users, etc.

Table 8. Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
Report in maximum 15 lines the main outcomes related to the KPIs validation, reporting the most relevant measured performances (including values), identifying which have been the most critical requirements (met or not), which are the potential improvements that next generation of mobile networks should bring, etc.

Table 9. Outcomes of the KVI validation.

Outcomes of the KVI validation
Report in maximum 15 lines the main outcomes related to the KVI validation, including numbers, if the expected targets has been fulfilled, users' feedbacks, etc.

6.1 Innovation aspects (half page)

The monthly report template provides the sub-project's view on its innovation potential. The TrialsNet Innovation Management use this as a light touch monitoring of sub-project Innovation Management. After 12 months of development and trials it is expected that the performed activity has enhanced the outlook on the sub-project's innovation. However, the sub-project may have found that prospects are not as strong. Complete the following table to highlight changes and comment on any major ones explaining why.

Table 10. Innovation take-out.

Aspect	Initial view	Concluding view
What innovation may emerge from the sub-project?	Please insert the sub-project's initial view.	Please insert the sub-project's concluding view at the end of the activity, and comment on any major changes and <u>why</u> .
Assessment of the Key Value (KV) category and any relevant value indicators (KVI)	Please insert the sub-project's initial view.	Please insert the sub-project's concluding view at the end of the activity, and comment on any major changes and <u>why</u> .

What 4P category does the sub-project target?	Please insert the sub-project's initial view.	Please insert the sub-project's concluding view at the end of the activity, and comment on any major changes and <u>why</u> .
How long it b before the sub-project brings this innovation to market?	Please insert the sub-project's initial view.	Please insert the sub-project's concluding view at the end of the activity, and comment on any major changes and <u>why</u> .

6.2 Dissemination and communication

In addition to the table below, **shortly report the 3 most relevant dissemination and communication activities performed by the project**, e.g., workshop organization, webinar, video publishing, etc.

Table 11. Dissemination and communication KPIs.

KPIs	Number
Organization of dissemination events (e.g., workshops, demo showcases, etc.)	
Participation to events (e.g., conferences, demo at exhibitions, etc.)	
Scientific publications	
Contributions to standards	
Open-Source repositories	
Patents (IPR)	
Communication activities (news, videos, blog posts, etc.)	
Social media (followers)	
Social media (impressions)	

6.3 Exploitation (half page)

Report here the exploitation plan based on to the work and outcomes of the sub-project.

7 Deviations (1 page)

Report in this section any deviation related to the performed activities and the mitigation plan that has been put in place to overcome the issues. Positive deviations (i.e., activities and/or results that exceeded the initial plan) should be also reported.

8 Conclusions (1 page)

Report the conclusions of the document.

Acknowledgment

TrialsNet project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon-JU-SNS-2022 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101095871.

References

- [1] TrialsNet Deliverable D3.1, "Use Cases definition for Infrastructure, Transportation and Security Safety (ITSS) domain", 30 April 2023
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- [3] "26th European Conference on Artificial Intelligence ECAI 2023", 30 September - 5 October 2023, link: <https://ecai2023.eu/>

Annex A – [Title]

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